

EVALUATING THE SYNTHETIC INERTIA OF A REAL SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAIC POWER FACILITY

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Abstract

As renewable energy integration on a large scale continues to expand, the inherent inertia within power systems diminishes, leading to an acceleration in the rate of frequency changes and diminishing the system's ability to promptly adapt to these fluctuations. Consequently, there arises a pressing demand for novel renewable energy installations to provide inertia to the system, a concept termed 'synthetic inertia'. This research delves into the examination of synthetic inertial response exhibited by an operational solar photovoltaic (PV) power plant situated in Spain, in compliance with the national grid code. Compliance with the synthetic inertia requirement by the generating unit is assessed through dynamic simulations, which are conducted at the Power Generation Unit (PGU) level. The dynamic simulations were performed using a validated model of a PV power system. The testing is conducted under three conditions: 1) At a load ranging from 0.25 to 0.50 times the nominal power (P_N) of the PGU; 2) At a load exceeding 0.80 times P_N of the PGU; and 3) At a load below P_N of the PGU. In addition, the three test cases are studied under both increases and decreases in frequency.

1 Introduction

According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), the integration of renewable energy into national power systems can be categorized into different phases, each defined by the level of penetration and the associated technical, regulatory, market, and institutional challenges. These phases range from phase 1, where the share of VRE in the system is minimal and its impact is highly localized, to phase 6, where substantial energy storage systems will be necessary to manage the very high share of VRE. By phase 4, the share of renewable energy is already considerable, requiring significant operational and regulatory adjustments. In countries that have reached phase 4, it is crucial to update regulatory frameworks to enable renewable energy technologies to provide system services and respond effectively to fluctuations in generation and demand. While most countries are still in phases 1 or 2, others, like Spain, have already reached high levels of variable renewable energy penetration, necessitating immediate and substantial changes to the regulatory structures governing the operation of renewable power plants. It is in this context that the new Spanish grid code is being implemented.

One of the issues to pay special attention to in this new energy context is that of power-frequency control in power systems. Thus, in a system where a shaft connects a turbine and a generator with a constant mechanical torque applied, two scenarios could unfold: i) if the load (or demand) increases, the electrical torque would rise, causing the system to slow down and the electrical frequency to decrease; ii) if the load

decreases, the electrical torque would drop, leading the system to accelerate and the electrical frequency to gradually increase. Given that numerous generators contribute to electricity generation within a network, frequency control must be managed across the entire power system. This necessitates a control system that regulates the mechanical power applied to the turbines connected to synchronous generators, ensuring the electrical frequency remains stable in response to any changes in demand. Therefore, the two primary variables that need to be controlled through the power production of generators within a power system are frequency and power flow through the lines. In addition to balancing generation and demand, the power output of each plant must align with the operation of the electricity market, which primarily dictates how much power each generating unit should supply and how much power should be exchanged between neighboring control areas.

However, when there is an increase in load, the energy required to immediately compensate for this increase comes from the kinetic energy of the rotating masses of the generators, which begin to slow down. This is known as the inertial response. The inertia constant, which is the kinetic energy stored in the rotating mass at synchronous speed divided by the machine's rated power, is a crucial parameter in electric power systems. In most renewable energy power plants, however, which rely on electronic interfaces, there are no turbines or large synchronous generators. Primary frequency control (PFC) in these plants is carried out through the operation of power electronic converters within the

renewable generation devices [1, 2]. Consequently, when frequency increases occur in the network, PV power plants must ensure a reduction in their active power output. Conversely, when frequency decreases, these installations must guarantee an increase in active power, striving to continuously balance generation and demand, similar to conventional power plants. This aspect is contemplated in the new Spanish grid code, MO TED/749/2020 [3].

In Spain, MO TED/749/2020 outlines the technical standards that generation facilities must adhere to, while the Spanish technical supervision standard, known as the ‘Norma Técnica de Supervisión’ (NTS) [4], the latest version of which was issued in July 2021, oversees compliance with the technical specifications outlined in MO TED/749/2020. This updated Spanish grid code not only incorporates the synthetic inertia requirement but also delineates the methodology that PV power plants in Spain should follow to meet this requirement.

In this sense, it is worth noting that the critical role of inertia in power networks is underscored by the new energy context, as mentioned above. As inertia in power systems declines due to the shutdown of conventional power plants, changes in demand have a greater impact, causing frequency variations to manifest more rapidly across the network—resulting in a faster power system dynamic. This necessitates quicker responses from generation units to adapt to the evolving conditions and highlights the need for new variable renewable energy plants to also be able to contribute inertia -or synthetic inertia- to the system. Synthetic inertia, also referred to as virtual or hidden inertia [5], is the artificial replication of inertial behavior by renewable generation units that are connected to the grid through electronic converters. In technical terms, inertia emulation involves electronic converters adjusting the active power output in proportion to the rate of change of the grid frequency.

However, it’s worth noting that at present, the synthetic inertia requirement is not obligatory but rather subject to voluntary adoption. Hence, it can be affirmed that Spain stands as a pioneer in incorporating the synthetic inertia technical requisite into its grid code. This stands in contrast to the EU’s Regulation EU 2016/631 [6], which mentions the necessity for synthetic inertia but leaves the discretion on its implementation and conditions to individual member states. In other nations like Germany, Italy, or the UK, where renewable energy penetration is also substantial, discussions have commenced regarding the synthetic inertia requirement. However, it has yet to be integrated into their grid codes, not even as an ‘optional requirement’.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 outlines the methods used to carry out the analyses in this study, including the configuration of the parameters for the PV system under examination. Section 3 details the results obtained when the PV system is subjected to the synthetic inertia requirements specified in the Spanish grid code. Lastly, Section 4 provides a summary of the key conclusions drawn from the study.

2 Methodology

The NTS has issued a dedicated document outlining guidelines for drafting the inertia emulation report in cases where it is applicable. This document specifies that the report will only be submitted to the Transmission System Operator (TSO) by generating units equipped to emulate this non-mandatory requirement. Compliance with this requirement by generating units can be assessed through dynamic simulations, which are mandated to be conducted solely at the Power Generation Unit (PGU) level, unless otherwise specified by the Power Park Module (PPM). In the current scenario, dynamic simulations were performed using a validated model of a PV power conversion system. PGUs denote the primary generation unit within the power plant, while PPMs encompass the entire plant. The simulation analyses are required to demonstrate the enhancement of unit response with the inertia emulation control activated, compared to simulations without it. Additionally, these simulations must adhere to the provisions outlined in Standard IEC 61400-21-1 [7]. Accordingly, Standard IEC 61400-21-1 defines the synthetic inertia requirement as the PGU’s capacity to support the grid by supplying additional active power during frequency events. This capability is to be assessed while the PGU operates continuously across various active power (P) load levels. The testing is conducted under the following three conditions: 1) At a load ranging from 0.25 to 0.50 times the nominal power (P_N) of the PGU; 2) At a load exceeding 0.80 times the nominal power of the PGU; and 3) At a load below the nominal power of the PGU. The nominal power should correspond to the available active power (P_{av}), which represents the potential power generation based on the primary available resource. In the third scenario, it is evident that the PGU is operating in a de-loaded control mode. Additionally, the load levels specified in the preceding three cases must be established amidst frequency fluctuations, both increases and decreases. Furthermore, the frequency variation should be significant enough to facilitate the analysis of differences between operating with and without the inertia emulation module enabled.

After integrating the PV system into DIgSILENT PowerFactory, the designated software for conducting simulations, the evaluation of the synthetic inertia capability requirement is carried out by analyzing the time series data of active power and frequency reference at the PGU terminals. Subsequently, the compliance of the PGU with the inertia emulation requirement is assessed based on the following parameters: i) Reaction time: This is defined as the duration from when the control signal for activating the PGU response is dispatched until the amplitude change reaches 10% of the step height of the measured output variable; ii) Response time: This measures the duration from the onset of the event - the change in the power response of the PGU - until its value falls within the predefined tolerance band of the target value; iii) Settling time: This is the duration from the start of the event - the change in the power response of the PGU - until its value consistently remains within the predefined tolerance band of the active power response; and iv) Predefined tolerance band: The evaluation of settling time is based on a

predefined tolerance band, defined as 5% of the active power variation by which the PGU responds to the frequency change.

Fig. 1 Characterization of the synthetic inertial response. Time parameters.

According to the current provisions outlined in the Spanish grid code, the compliance evaluation of the system with the synthetic inertia technical requirement is simplified to considering only two parameters: the system will be deemed compliant if both reaction and response times are reduced with the activation of the inertia module. Besides the variables mentioned earlier, there are additional parameters that could be evaluated, visually depicted in Fig. 1, albeit they are not the focus of this study. On the other hand, four specific parameters must be configured to execute the simulations. These parameters include the frequency change and frequency gradient applied, as well as the inertia trigger and recovery values. The latter are defined as the frequency thresholds at which the PV power conversion system initiates and ceases boosting active power, respectively. In this instance, to examine the inertial response (IR) of the PV power conversion system, frequency increases and decreases are set at 1 Hz each. Moreover, the applied frequency gradient is established at 0.50 Hz/s for tests involving frequency increases, and at -0.16 Hz/s for tests involving frequency decreases. Lastly, the frequency trigger and frequency recovery values for assessing the IR are set at 50.01 Hz and 49.99 Hz, respectively, for both frequency increase and decrease tests. Tables 1 and 2 provide a summary of these parameters (note that in test cases 3 and 6, the system operates in a de-loaded control mode, as previously mentioned).

Table 1 Configuration of parameters for test cases 1 through 3 to analyze the inertial response of the PV system.

Test Case	Frequency Increases		
	1	2	3
P (pu)	0.30	0.85	0.85 ($P_{av} = P_N$)
Change in f Applied (Hz)	50-51	50-51	50-51
Gradient of f Applied (Hz/s)	0.50	0.50	0.50
f Inertia, Trigger (Hz)	50.01	50.01	50.01
f Inertia, Recovery (Hz)	50.01	50.01	50.01

Table 2 Configuration of parameters for test cases 4 through 6 to analyze the inertial response of the PV system.

Test Case	Frequency Decreases		
	4	5	6
P (pu)	0.30	0.85	0.85 ($P_{av} = P_N$)
Change in f Applied (Hz)	50-49	50-49	50-49
Gradient of f Applied (Hz/s)	-0.16	-0.16	-0.16
f Inertia, Trigger (Hz)	49.99	49.99	49.99
f Inertia, Recovery (Hz)	49.99	49.99	49.99

3 Results

This section presents the simulation responses of the PV system model when the inertia emulation module is enabled and disabled, and both under frequency increases and decreases, as explained in Section 2.

Table 3 displays the outcomes of the synthetic inertia tests conducted during frequency increases, whereas Table 4 exhibits the results of the same tests conducted during frequency decreases.

The simulation results of the PV system under the test scenarios outlined in Section 2 are depicted in Fig. 2 for frequency increases and Fig. 3 for frequency decreases. In these figures, red indicates frequency, black illustrates the active power response of the PV system when both PFC and IR capabilities are engaged, while grey dotted lines represent the active power response of the PV system solely contributing to PFC in the grid.

The reaction time measured upon activation of the inertia emulation module is consistently lower in all scenarios (as can be observed in Tables 3 and 4), whether experiencing frequency increases or decreases, compared to when the module remains inactive. The description of this parameter, as outlined in Section 2, provides insight into the ramp slope value of the PV system power response. It is notably greater when the inertia emulation module is activated, thereby facilitating a faster contribution to power-frequency regulation within the network. Concerning response time, as depicted in Tables 3 and 4, the values recorded with the activated inertia module consistently demonstrate lower figures than those when the module remains inactive, mirroring the trend observed in reaction time. The obtained response time values suggest that the active power signal of the PV system aligns with the target value's tolerance band sooner when inertia emulation is engaged compared to when it is not. The contrast in both reaction time and response time between the instances of activated and deactivated inertia modules is also evident when visualized graphically in Figs. 2 and 3.

4 Conclusion

As renewable power installations become more prevalent, power systems experience a reduction in inertia, leading to faster frequency changes. This necessitates a quicker response from systems to mitigate the effects of frequency disturbances,

Fig. 2 Synthetic inertia capability of the PV system under frequency increases - PFC and combined PFC & IR. (a) Test Case 1: $0.25P_N < P < 0.50P_N$, (b) Test Case 2: $P > 0.80P_N$, (c) Test Case 3: $P = 85\%P_N$; $P_{av} = P_N$.

posing a significant challenge that must be addressed collaboratively by the entities involved in the generation, transmission, and distribution of electricity. Spain currently stands out as the only country that has incorporated into its grid code the capability for PV power plants and other renewable installations to contribute to power-frequency regulation in a manner similar

Table 3 Numerical results of the inertia emulation test cases during frequency increases. Evaluation conducted at the power conversion level of the PV system.

Frequency Increases						
Test Case	1		2		3	
P Range (Test Case)	$0.25P_N < P < 0.50P_N$		$P > 0.80P_N$		$P = 85\%P_N$ $P_{av} = P_N$	
Inertia Emulation	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Reaction Time (s)	0.25	0.04	0.25	0.04	0.19	0.03
Response Time (s)	1.93	0.61	2.92	0.57	1.91	0.57

Table 4 Numerical results of the inertia emulation test cases during frequency decreases. Evaluation conducted at the power conversion level of the PV system.

Frequency Decreases						
Test Case	4		5		6	
P Range (Test Case)	$0.25P_N < P < 0.50P_N$		$P > 0.80P_N$		$P = 85\%P_N$ $P_{av} = P_N$	
Inertia Emulation	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Reaction Time (s)	0.00	-	0.00	0.00	0.24	0.04
Response Time (s)	0.00	-	0.00	0.00	1.78	0.47

to conventional power plants by providing an IR. Additionally, Spain has established a methodology to verify whether a PV power plant meets this ‘synthetic inertia’ requirement. While compliance with this requirement is still optional, it is widely expected to become mandatory in the near future.

Within this framework, this study examines the responses of an operational PV power plant in Spain when evaluated against the synthetic inertia requirement outlined in the Spanish grid code. The plant’s IR is assessed based on measurements taken at the power conversion system level—the component equipped with control algorithms that enable the provision of said IR.

At the power conversion level of the PV system, the integration of the inertia emulation module significantly decreases the response and reaction time values obtained. Therefore, it can be asserted that the PV system in question meets the synthetic inertia technical requirement outlined in the Spanish grid code.

This article, offering a practical perspective in its field of study, underscores the importance of using dynamic simulation models to assess the compliance of renewable installations with the various requirements set out in grid codes. It also emphasizes the need for a dedicated document to guide compliance testing of solar PV facilities with the synthetic inertia technical requirement, as current practices have largely been adapted from those developed for wind power plants.

Fig. 3 Synthetic inertia capability of the PV system under frequency decreases - PFC and combined PFC & IR. (a) Test Case 1: $0.25P_N < P < 0.50P_N$, (b) Test Case 2: $P > 0.80P_N$, (c) Test Case 3: $P = 85\%P_N$; $P_{av} = P_N$.

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